

Direct Ink Writing antenna radiator for Conformal Load-bearing Antenna Structure

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01. Introduction

1. Research background
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Research background

❖ CLAS (Conformal Load-bearing Antenna Structure)

- What is Conformal Load-bearing Antenna Structure (CLAS) ?
 - Next-generation antenna integrated into the aircraft's Outer Mold Line (OML)
 - Replaces protruding antennas for improved aerodynamics
- Composed of multiple parts, including an antenna radiator for signal transmission and reception

Fig. 1. Schematic of Conformal load bearing antenna structure (CLAS).

Research background

❖ Antenna radiator and limitations of conventional antenna fabrication

- Traditional antenna fabrication is limited by substrate type and shape
- **CLAS often follows curved aircraft surfaces (OML), requiring non-flat substrates**
→ Growing need for antennas on curved or complex geometries
- Direct Ink Writing (DIW) offers a flexible solution for conformal antenna fabrication

Fig. 2. Copper etching microstrip antenna.

Research background

❖ DIW (Direct Ink Writing) Process [1-7]

- What is Direct Ink Writing (DIW)?
 - A type of 3D printing that directly deposits ink onto a substrate
- Enables multifunctional structures using application-specific materials
- Compatible with various substrate shapes, including flat and curved surfaces

Fig. 3. Schematic of Direct ink writing (DIW) fabrication process.

Research background

❖ Research trends in DIW process

➤ Skylar-Scott et al., PNAS, 2016

- Demonstrated laser-assisted DIW
- Using Silver nanoparticle ink
- Enabled 3D printing without separate sintering

➤ Asrar Alam et al., J. Energy Storage, 2022

- Developed Ag/TiO₂ nanoparticle composite ink
- Electrode material for high-performance supercapacitors
- Cured at 60 °C for 24 hours without sintering

Fig. 4. DIW fabrication process research trends: (A) 2016, PNAS, (B) 2022, J Energy storage.

Research purpose

❖ Study on CLAS with DIW antenna radiator

- Design requirements for printed antenna radiator patterns
 - Targeting resonant frequency and bandwidth suitable for structural reliability and operational conditions
- Development and performance evaluation of DIW-based antennas for integration
- Investigation of printed antenna implementation in conformal load-bearing structures

Fig. 5. Research purpose.

02. DIW antenna radiator fabrication and evaluation

- 1. Development of Materials and Process**
 - 2. Fabrication and evaluation of DIW antenna**
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Development of DIW Materials and Process

❖ Selection of materials for DIW antenna radiator

- Silver Microparticle Paste (AgMP, ACH35001LV, Protavic Korea)
 - Ensures strong adhesion to substrate
- Silver Nanowires (AgNW, C3NW02, C3nano, USA)
 - Enhances electrical conductivity of printed patterns

Fig. 6. SEM image of DIW composition materials: (A) AgMP, (B) AgNW.

Development of Materials and Process

❖ Development of DIW antenna radiator material

- **Development and Application of DIW Material Fabrication Method Based on IPA Content Control**
 - AgNP paste and AgNW solution were mixed for 45 minutes
 - IPA was evaporated using a vacuum oven
 - After vacuum processing, a paste mixer was used to uniformly disperse AgMP and AgNW
- The material containing **1.2 wt%_{AgNW}** ($\sigma_{elec} = 4.16 (\pm 0.38) \times 10^5 \text{S/m}$) was used.

Fig. 7. (A) DIW material manufacturing technique based on IPA content control method, (B) SEM image of DIW material.

Development of Materials and Process

❖ Development of DIW antenna radiator manufacturing process

- Viscosity of DIW paste was tested using a trial extrusion setup
- Extruder mounted on Ender-3 Pro (Creality, China) for 3-axis DIW printing (Fig. A)
- Controlled via display panel and G-code
- Verified stable and consistent print quality (Fig. B)

(A)

Fig. 8. (A) Extruder for testing and DIW equipment, (B) image of DIW line.

Fabrication and evaluation of DIW antenna

❖ DIW Antenna Pattern Design and Fabrication

- Designed for **resonance frequency (f_R) of 5.03 GHz** based on copper conductivity
- **DIW antenna pattern fabrication procedure**
 - Antenna pattern fabricated using DIW equipment and cured in an oven
 - Feed line soldered and antenna connector attached

Fig. 9. (A) CAD Modeling of EM radiator, (B) manufactured DIW antenna pattern.

Fabrication and evaluation of DIW antenna

❖ Performance evaluation of DIW antenna radiator

- Antennas were fabricated using both copper etching and direct ink writing (DIW)
- Performance was evaluated in an anechoic chamber

Fig. 10. Performance test of antenna fabricated DIW process on anechoic chamber.

Fabrication and evaluation of DIW antenna

❖ Comparison of Antenna Return Loss Performance

	Resonance frequency(f_R)	Reflection loss (RL)	Bandwidth (BW)
Copper etching antenna	5.04 GHz	-35.304 dB	248 MHz
DIW antenna	4.925 GHz	-33.023 dB	241 MHz

Except for the resonant frequency shift,
 the DIW and copper-etched antennas show nearly
 identical performance across the frequency band

Fig. 11. Return loss of EM radiator fabricated by copper etching and DIW.

Fabrication and evaluation of DIW antenna

❖ Comparison of antenna gain patterns

- Copper-etched and DIW antennas showed no significant difference in radiation pattern and peak gain.

→ **The DIW method demonstrated both structural flexibility and stable electrical performance.**

Fig. 12. 2D and 3D gain patterns of EM radiator: (A) copper etching antenna, (B) DIW antenna

03. Integration into CLAS

- 1. Fabrication and Evaluation of MAS**
 - 2. Integration of DIW antenna into CLAS**
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Fabrication and Evaluation of MAS

❖ Design of MAS (Multifunctional Antenna Structure)

- Designed and fabricated a Multifunctional Antenna Structure (MAS)
- Structure composed of facesheet, core, and DIW antenna radiator
- Investigated effects of dielectric loading

Fig. 13. Schematic of multifunctional antenna structure (MAS).

Fabrication and Evaluation of MAS

❖ Components and fabrication of MAS

- Facesheet : RT/duroid®6002 (Rogers corporation, USA)
- Sandwich core : Duraform ProX PA (3D system, USA) (Selective laser sintering, SLS)
- Adhesive film : AF 163-2K (3MTM, Scotch-Weld™, USA)

Fig. 14. Components and fabrication of multifunctional antenna structure (MAS).

Fabrication and Evaluation of MAS

❖ Comparison of antenna performance evaluation

	Resonance frequency(f_R)	Reflection loss (RL)	Bandwidth (BW)
DIW	4.925 GHz	-33.02 dB	241 MHz
MAS	4.840 GHz	-20.51 dB	232 MHz

DIW → MAS
 $f_R = 4.925 \text{ GHz} \rightarrow 4.840 \text{ GHz}$
 ※ **Effect of Dielectric loading**

Fig. 15. Antenna performance results: (A) return loss, (B) resonant frequency and bandwidth.

Fabrication and Evaluation of MAS

❖ Comparison of antenna performance evaluation

- Gain pattern and beamwidth remained similar with and without MAS integration
- A shift in resonant frequency was observed due to dielectric loading
- With frequency adjustment, the antenna can be used in CLAS with comparable performance

Fig. 16. 2D and 3D gain patterns of EM radiator (A) DIW antenna, (B) MAS.

Integration of DIW antenna into CLAS

❖ Fabrication of CLAS with DIW antenna radiator

- Antenna-integrated structure fabricated using a directly printed radiator
- Structure composed of Outer facesheet, Core, Antenna radiator, Inner facesheet
- Verified feasibility of applying the printed radiator to the integrated structure

Fig. 17. Fabricated DIW process antenna applied CLAS.

Integration of DIW antenna into CLAS

❖ Fabrication of CLAS with DIW antenna radiator

5.3 GHz	f_R	RL	BW
DIW	5.035 GHz	-44.58 dB	250 MHz
CLAS	4.83 GHz	-29.01 dB	315 MHz

5.4 GHz	f_R	RL	BW
DIW	5.275 GHz	-35.42 dB	290 MHz
CLAS	5.1 GHz	-16.31 dB	290 MHz

Fig. 18. Antenna performance results according to DIW antenna pattern adjustment

04. Conclusion

Conclusion

❖ Direct Ink Writing antenna radiator for Conformal Load-bearing Antenna Structure

• DIW Antenna Fabrication and Application to CLAS

- ✓ Developed a high-conductivity nanocomposite material for DIW antennas
- ✓ Established a DIW fabrication process for antenna patterning
- ✓ Verified the effect of dielectric loading (resonant frequency shift)
- ✓ Achieved CLAS performance within the target frequency band
- ✓ Confirmed the feasibility of applying DIW antennas to CLAS

➤ **This approach enables lightweight, conformal, and multifunctional antenna integration for future aerospace systems**

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Thank you

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Appendices

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